
DMP du projet "Rôles de la régulation hydrique et thermique dans les réponses écologiques au changement climatique"

Plan de gestion de données créé à l'aide de DMP OPIDoR, basé sur le modèle "ANR - DMP template (english)" fourni par Agence nationale de la recherche (ANR).

Renseignements sur le plan

Titre du plan	DMP du projet "Rôles de la régulation hydrique et thermique dans les réponses écologiques au changement climatique"
Livrable	0.4
Version	Version initiale
Objet/périmètre du plan	<p>The project manager will coordinate networking activities, internal and external communication, and exchange of protocols and data. Due to the geographical distance among partners, we will organize both web meetings every 1-2 months including and one annual meeting including all participants. A mailing list will allow regular exchanges and documents, data and communication tools will be stored in a collaborative web platform available to all members. Important to this procedure, we plan to report each meeting with detailed minutes and recommendations to better implement our working strategy. Thanks to this, the project manager will be able to check that all partners conform to their task schedule and deliverables, and solutions to cope with delays-failures will be anticipated. Staff recruitment will be managed by each partner in agreement with the coordinator and implicated partners. The project manager will carry out the budget and administrative report in collaboration with financial services of each partner.</p>
Langue	eng
Date de création	2022-01-21
Date de dernière modification	2022-01-21
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Renseignements sur le projet

Titre du projet Rôles de la régulation hydrique et thermique dans les réponses écologiques au changement climatique

Acronyme AQUATHERM

Résumé

Le changement climatique modifie les conditions thermiques et la disponibilité de l'eau dans le temps et l'espace. La sensibilité et la résilience des animaux ectothermes face à ce changement sont déterminés par leurs capacités et tolérances physiologiques et comportementales. Les réponses individuelles aux changements des conditions thermiques et de la disponibilité de l'eau *in situ* dépendent spécifiquement de la thermorégulation (c'est-à-dire la régulation physiologique et comportementale de la température corporelle) et de l'hydrorégulation (c'est-à-dire la régulation physiologique et comportementale du budget hydrique). Comment les interactions entre la thermorégulation et l'hydrorégulation influencent la vulnérabilité au changement climatique demeure cependant pratiquement inconnu. Ici, nous utiliserons l'écophysiologie et l'écologie comportementale pour améliorer notre compréhension de ce problème critique chez les ectothermes terrestres. En se concentrant sur les reptiles squamates (lézards et serpents), nous combinerons des modèles biophysiques mécanistes, des études empiriques de traits physiologiques et comportementaux aux niveaux individuel et populationnel chez deux espèces modèles dans deux massifs montagneux en France, des simulations de niches climatiques et des analyses comparatives. Nous serons ainsi en mesure de décrire et de comprendre pour la première fois les patrons de covariation entre la thermorégulation et l'hydrorégulation afin d'améliorer notre capacité à prédire les effets écologiques de deux facteurs du changement climatique.

Sources de financement

- Agence Nationale de la Recherche : ANR-17-CE02-0013

Date de début 2018-01-01

Date de fin 2023-12-31

Partenaires

- iEES Paris (200517555P)
- CEREEP-Ecotron IleDeFrance (200810875R)
- CEBC (201420642F)
- SETE (201119468T)

Produits de recherche :

1. Quantification of climate conditions and microhabitats (Jeu de données)
2. Quantification of geographic variation in hydroregulation and thermoregulation (Jeu de données)
3. Species-level data on hydroregulation and thermoregulation (Jeu de données)
4. Quantification of geographic variation in climate sensitivity and acclimation responses (Jeu de données)
5. Spatially explicit mechanistic niche model at regional scale (Modèle)
6. Development of a behavioural model to describe thermoregulation and hydroregulation (Modèle)
7. Bioclimate data at high spatio-temporal resolution (Modèle)
8. Development of a dynamic energy budget (DEB) model
9. Assessment of immediate physiological responses (Jeu de données)
10. Assessment of behavioural responses (Jeu de données)
11. Quantification of long-term sensitivity and acclimation responses

Contributeurs

Contributeurs	Rôles
Jean Clobert	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personne contact pour les données (Bioclimate models)
Jean-François Le Galliard	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordinateur du projet • Personne contact pour les données (Species-level data, Climate data, Geographic variation, Behavioural model, Behavioural response) • Responsable du plan de gestion de données
Olivier Lourdais	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personne contact pour les données (Geography plasticity, Immediate responses, Acclimation response)
Andréaz Dupoué	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personne contact pour les données (Mechanistic models, DEB model)

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1. Data description and collection or re-use of existing data

1a. How will new data be collected or produced and/or how will existing data be re-used?

Data will be collected by project participants using field surveys of wild populations, laboratory studies of semi-captive and wild animals and laboratory experiments with semi-captive and wild animals. In addition, data published in the previous literature will be re-used to perform meta-analysis and comparative analyses.

1b. What data (for example the kind, formats, and volumes), will be collected or produced?

Question sans réponse.

2. Documentation and data quality

2a. What metadata and documentation (for example the methodology of data collection and way of organising data) will accompany the data?

Question sans réponse.

2b. What data quality control measures will be used?

Data will be primarily checked by collectors then by main person in charge of the deliverable and eventually by the person responsible for data storage.

3. Storage and backup during the research process

3a. How will data and metadata be stored and backed up during the research?

Data and metadata will be stored and backed up on personal computers during the research.

3b. How will data security and protection of sensitive data be taken care during the research

Question sans réponse.

4. Legal and ethical requirements, code of conduct

Bioclimate data at high spatio-temporal resolution

4a. If personal data are processed, how will compliance with legislation on personal data and on security be ensured?

Question sans réponse.

4b. How will other legal issues, such as intellectual property rights and ownership, be managed? What legislation is applicable?

Question sans réponse.

4c. What ethical issues and codes of conduct are there, and how will they be taken into account?

Question sans réponse.

Development of a behavioural model to describe thermoregulation and hydroregulation

4a. If personal data are processed, how will compliance with legislation on personal data and on security be ensured?

Question sans réponse.

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Development of a dynamic energy budget (DEB) model

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Question sans réponse.

4c. What ethical issues and codes of conduct are there, and how will they be taken into account?

Question sans réponse.

Assessment of immediate physiological responses

4a. If personal data are processed, how will compliance with legislation on personal data and on security be ensured?

Question sans réponse.

4b. How will other legal issues, such as intellectual property rights and ownership, be managed? What legislation is applicable?

Question sans réponse.

4c. What ethical issues and codes of conduct are there, and how will they be taken into account?

Question sans réponse.

Assessment of behavioural responses

4a. If personal data are processed, how will compliance with legislation on personal data and on security be ensured?

Question sans réponse.

4b. How will other legal issues, such as intellectual property rights and ownership, be managed? What legislation is applicable?

Question sans réponse.

4c. What ethical issues and codes of conduct are there, and how will they be taken into account?

Question sans réponse.

Quantification of long-term sensitivity and acclimation responses

4a. If personal data are processed, how will compliance with legislation on personal data and on security be ensured?

Question sans réponse.

4b. How will other legal issues, such as intellectual property rights and ownership, be managed? What legislation is applicable?

Question sans réponse.

4c. What ethical issues and codes of conduct are there, and how will they be taken into account?

Question sans réponse.

Quantification of climate conditions and microhabitats

4a. If personal data are processed, how will compliance with legislation on personal data and on security be ensured?

Question sans réponse.

4b. How will other legal issues, such as intellectual property rights and ownership, be managed? What legislation is applicable?

Question sans réponse.

4c. What ethical issues and codes of conduct are there, and how will they be taken into account?

Question sans réponse.

Quantification of geographic variation in hydroregulation and thermoregulation

4a. If personal data are processed, how will compliance with legislation on personal data and on security be ensured?

Question sans réponse.

4b. How will other legal issues, such as intellectual property rights and ownership, be managed? What legislation is applicable?

Question sans réponse.

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Quantification of geographic variation in climate sensitivity and acclimation responses

4a. If personal data are processed, how will compliance with legislation on personal data and on security be ensured?

Question sans réponse.

4b. How will other legal issues, such as intellectual property rights and ownership, be managed? What legislation is applicable?

Question sans réponse.

4c. What ethical issues and codes of conduct are there, and how will they be taken into account?

Question sans réponse.

Spatially explicit mechanistic niche model at regional scale

4a. If personal data are processed, how will compliance with legislation on personal data and on security be ensured?

Question sans réponse.

4b. How will other legal issues, such as intellectual property rights and ownership, be managed? What legislation is applicable?

Question sans réponse.

4c. What ethical issues and codes of conduct are there, and how will they be taken into account?

Question sans réponse.

Species-level data on hydroregulation and thermoregulation

4a. If personal data are processed, how will compliance with legislation on personal data and on security be ensured?

Question sans réponse.

4b. How will other legal issues, such as intellectual property rights and ownership, be managed? What legislation is applicable?

Question sans réponse.

4c. What ethical issues and codes of conduct are there, and how will they be taken into account?

Question sans réponse.

5. Data sharing and long-term preservation

5a. How and when will data be shared? Are there possible restrictions to data sharing or embargo reasons?

Data will be shared using full Open Access rules without embargo upon publication.

5b. How will data for preservation be selected, and where data will be preserved long-term (for example a data repository or archive)?

Final data will be stored in data archive Zenodo upon publication.

5c. What methods or software tools are needed to access and use data?

Question sans réponse.

5d. How will the application of a unique and persistent identifier (such as a Digital Object Identifier (DOI)) to each data set be ensured?

Each dataset will be given a unique DOI.

6. Data management responsibilities and resources

Bioclimate data at high spatio-temporal resolution

6a. Who (for example role, position, and institution) will be responsible for data management (i.e. the data steward)?

The project coordinator will be responsible for data management upon publication.

6b. What resources (for example financial and time) will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable)?

Question sans réponse.

Development of a behavioural model to describe thermoregulation and hydroregulation

6a. Who (for example role, position, and institution) will be responsible for data management (i.e. the data steward)?

Question sans réponse.

6b. What resources (for example financial and time) will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable)?

Question sans réponse.

Development of a dynamic energy budget (DEB) model

6a. Who (for example role, position, and institution) will be responsible for data management (i.e. the data steward)?

Question sans réponse.

6b. What resources (for example financial and time) will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable)?

Question sans réponse.

Assessment of immediate physiological responses

6a. Who (for example role, position, and institution) will be responsible for data management (i.e. the data steward)?

Question sans réponse.

6b. What resources (for example financial and time) will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable)?

Question sans réponse.

Assessment of behavioural responses

6a. Who (for example role, position, and institution) will be responsible for data management (i.e. the data steward)?

Question sans réponse.

6b. What resources (for example financial and time) will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable)?

Question sans réponse.

Quantification of long-term sensitivity and acclimation responses

6a. Who (for example role, position, and institution) will be responsible for data management (i.e. the data steward)?

Question sans réponse.

6b. What resources (for example financial and time) will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable)?

Question sans réponse.

Quantification of climate conditions and microhabitats

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Question sans réponse.

6b. What resources (for example financial and time) will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable)?

Question sans réponse.

Quantification of geographic variation in hydroregulation and thermoregulation

6a. Who (for example role, position, and institution) will be responsible for data management (i.e. the data steward)?

Question sans réponse.

6b. What resources (for example financial and time) will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable)?

Question sans réponse.

Quantification of geographic variation in climate sensitivity and acclimation responses

6a. Who (for example role, position, and institution) will be responsible for data management (i.e. the data steward)?

Question sans réponse.

6b. What resources (for example financial and time) will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable)?

Question sans réponse.

Spatially explicit mechanistic niche model at regional scale

6a. Who (for example role, position, and institution) will be responsible for data management (i.e. the data steward)?

Question sans réponse.

6b. What resources (for example financial and time) will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable)?

Question sans réponse.

Species-level data on hydroregulation and thermoregulation

6a. Who (for example role, position, and institution) will be responsible for data management (i.e. the data steward)?

Question sans réponse.

6b. What resources (for example financial and time) will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable)?

Question sans réponse.